

Handbook of Ubiquitous Music 2021 — a short presentation.

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***Abstract.** In this short presentation, I will cover recent developments for the second book dedicated to the interdisciplinary research of Ubimus. Since the first Ubiquitous Music book publication¹ in 2014, creative research has broadened with ever-expanding practice-based methodologies. This has enabled the contextual review of diverse musical practices to advance discussions on ubimus theory and methods, ubimus technologies, ecologically grounded practices and ubimus, and ubimus educational perspectives and the digital humanities. The Handbook of Ubiquitous Music 2021 will compile and present these developments as they have evolved.*

¹ *Ubiquitous Music*. edited by Damián Keller, Victor Lazzarini, and Marcelo Soares Pimenta. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2014.